

Assessment and Morphological characteristics of *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n. sp., from *Turdoides striata*, 1823 (Leiothrichidae) in Sindh - Pakistan

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ABSTRACT:

The research study was carried out on helminths of bird, Jungle babbler from taluka Kandiaro district Naushahro Feroze, Sindh during, 2015-16. The total (90) specimens were collected from (24) birds that belong to the genus; *Oligorchis* Fuhrmann, (1906) were found from terminal part of the large intestine, near the cloacal aperture of the bird. Present specimens were observed dissimilar from their habitats which have medium sized body with a maximum width at the level of gravid segments. The worms were relatively delicate, whitish and opaque when alive and the scolex muscular, wider than long. Rostellum provides two rows of 16 hooks and shorter neck followed by series of 288 segments. Gravid segments were greater in number than the mature proglottids and all segments wider than long. Prominent rostellum was along with minute sized sac with suckers muscular and oval in shape, dome shaped larger ovary and vitelline gland oval in shape behind it with the cirrus sac proturated almost in all segments. Tests three to four in numbers, oval in shape, eggs elongated and spindle shaped. The high intensity of infectivity was found during mid of winter and summer season, January and May with less population in June, consequent to the significant differences. It is further suggested that, the other birds of this region should be observed for checking the helminth.

Keyword: *Oligorchis kandiarisansis*, *Proglottids*, *Turdoides striata*, and *Scolex*.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan provides strong and rich zone for variety of visiting and resident birds [1, 2]. The birds are the God gifted creatures and they are also used by human beings for different purposes since from decades, it is an estimated (10,417) present through-out the world [3]. Similarly, birds are considered only terrestrial species that shares peculiarity with the humans [4] and having ability to fly national and international borders within a few hours and billion of bird species migrate from one continent to another continent twice in a year one with-in few weeks [5]. Jungle babbler, *Turdoides striata* Dumont de Sainte Croix, 1823 (Leiothrichidae) family was found in the Indian sub-continent is well known as *Saath bhai* or *seven sisters* in Hindi [6] it means seven siblings [7]. They possess yellow coloured eyes and nearly dusky and creamy in colour birds [8,9] with week in flight [10, 11] that possess round short wings and they are non-migratory bird [12, 13], feeds on insect matter, but can also eat grains, barriers and nectar [14]. The [15] studied about its food and feeding ecology of jungle babbler in district, Jammu and tend to be parasitized by the *Hierococcyx varrix* and *Clamator jacobinus* [16] feeding behaviour of jungle babbler immensely described by [17]. Bearing burden of helminth parasites human are highly at risk due to the presence of type E toxin and about an estimated (8000) birds died in (2000) and (25000) [18] such as; type C, a disease avian botulism, *Clostridium botulinum* is food poisoning of variety of wild birds also found in some other living organisms, humans are free from tis infection but other types of botulism toxins are present [19], and transport arthropode-brone viruses [20]. The migratory and wintering birds were being reared high density of helminths [21]. Unlike; CWD, West Nile fever is a zoonosis and it is brilliant example in North American humans

impacts related with disease emergence from wild birds and affect human, horses, bats (Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, 2000) many wild, domestic animals and wild birds are the host for *C. jejuni*.

Near about (4000) species of cestode helminthes have been reported from variety of vertebrates' hosts [22, 23, 24, 25]. Helminth parasites larval micro-flaria of *Diplotriaeana* and nematode species (*Diplotriaeana tricuspis*) were observed [26, 27]. The disease which transfer from animals to man such as; *Enterocytozoon* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Encephalitozoon* spp., and *Giardia* spp., were frequently reported in birds [28, 29, 30]. Now adays; Parasitologists are busy to evaluate the cestode on the genetic basis of the host specificity in avian hosts [31, 32, 33, 34, 35]. The (10) time badly effect with fleas and cause serve skin irritations and blotching due to the bites of bird mites [36] and ring necked pheasants mostly found positive with parasites in Kansas [37]. Gastrointestinal tract is the path of digestion and absorption of food of the avifauna but bacteria, virus, nutritional deficiencies and other infective agents cause intestinal problems in these hosts [38, 39]. The cestodes, trematodes and nematodes mostly affect poultry birds and there is a possibility of infestation from birds to human [40]. Avian haemo parasites cause failure in reproduction, retardation of growth, low productivity, negative effects on behaviour and mortality to their hosts [41, 42]. Therefore, the research study was carried out on the new specie; *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n.sp. which was recovered from an avian host, was morphologically different from other congress of cestodes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The wild feathered creature jungle babbler, *T. striata* were kept

under perceptions for checking the proximity of helminth parasites, hence the examination was helped out through the ensuing years during, 2015-16. The host winged creature were gathered from taluka Kandiaro of district, Naushahro Feroze, Sindh, Pakistan and brought under Parasitology research laboratory conditions at Department of Zoology, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur. Above all else the glass slides were cleaned by pouring them 100% of ethanol and left for 15-20 minutes in the coplin jar. At that point slides were cleaned with cotton swabs and handkerchief too. At that point discharged three to four drops of ethanol for the anaesthetization to host, after that expelled the feathers from the sternum area last on analyzed and isolated entire instinctive organs at long last, kept each in pattery dishes contained typical saline solution. By the assistance of stereo dissecting microscope for each organ was precisely observed. Than parasites were laid on glass slides and wrapped the string over the cover slip and kept it for couple of hours. After that thread were opened and slide containing parasites were poured in borax carmine for colour mounting, after colour mounting, parasites were washed and one to two drops were put of Canada balsam and by putting cover slip, slides were kept in oven box for appropriate temperature. Photography of the new specimens were brought with camera Meiji infinity, 1DK-3000. Estimation of the body and distinctive life structures of the specimens were taken in millimeters (mm) yet eggs estimation were taken in micrometers (μm). After development of changeless / permanent slides of helminths, were intentionally considered in point by point under the magnifying lens of microscope, the cestodes and trematodes were planned by the assistance of Camera Lucida.

Thus, the samples were taken on Family: Hymenolepididae Railliet and Henery, 1909; Sub-Family: Hymenolepidinae Perrier, 1897; Genus: *Oligorchis* Fuhrmann, 1906; *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n.sp. Location: Intestine; Host: Jungle babbler; Locality: Naushahro Feroze Sindh, Pakistan; Number of specimen: 90 from 24 hosts. Holotype specimens were placed in the Parasitology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, SALU, Khairpur for future planning, scientist and researchers for reference motivation. Whereas; the data on prevalence of *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n. sp. helminth parasites in *T. striata* were taken throughout year and finally statistically analyse was done with the help of SXW software version, 1.8. USA.

RESULTS

The specimens were collected from the intestine of the Jungle babbler having total length of measuring 51.65 by 1.34 in sized with the maximum width at the level of gravid segment. Worms were relatively delicate, whitish and opaque when alive. The scolex muscular, wider than long measured, 0.207 by 0.267 were in size. Rostellum provides two rows of 16 hooks measured, 0.603-0.869 X 0.120 – 0.120 in size. Short neck measured 0.154 by 0.233 in size. Neck followed by series of 288 segments. Gravid segments were 252 in number measured 0.066-0.075 X 0.45-0.558. Mature proglottids were 36 in number measured 0.258-1 X 0.25-0.926. All segments were wider than longer and prominent rostellum measured 0.060 by 0.075 in size whereas; rostellum sac measured 0.02 by 0.064 in sized and suckers muscular, oval measured, 0.90- 0.105 X 0.064-0.098 in size. Vitelline gland was found in oval shape behind the ovary measured 0.083 by 0.133 in sized and dome shaped larger ovary measured 0.133-0.141 X 0.133-0.175 in size. Cirrus sac protruated almost in all segments measured 0.4 - 0.475 X 0.125 – 0.141 in size. Testes three to four in number, oval in shape measured 0.108 – 0.133 X 0.091 – 0.091 in size and eggs were also found in elongated, spindle shaped

which measured 0.033 - 0.058 X 0.033 -0.05 in size, respectively. (Fig. 1 and 2) that consists over, Fig. 1. *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n. sp. A: Scolex; B: Hooks; C: Mature segment; D: Gravid segment, and Fig. 2. Photograph of E: Scolex; F: Mature segment; G: Gravid segment.

Fig. 1. *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n. sp. A: Scolex; B: Hooks; C: Mature segment; D: Gravid segment

Fig. 2. Photograph of E: Scolex; F: Mature segment; G: Gravid segment

Remarks about the genus

Oligorchis kandiarisansis n. sp. is planned to contain the cestode unruffled from the intestine of Jungle babbler bird divided the Family: Hymenolepididae Railliet and Henery, 1909; Sub-Family: Hymenolepidinae Perrier, 1897; Genus: *Oligorchis* Fuhrmann, 1906; *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n.sp reported first time in Sindh, Pakistan. The other species of this genus is *Oligorchis lahorensis* Khan and Habibullah, 1971 collected from the intestine of *Acredotheres ginginiamus* / *Corves splendens splendens* of Lahore that differs from present species having larger body in size; scolex larger in size; rostellum smaller in size; hooks are ten in number and smaller in size; suckers spinose larger in size; neck absent; mature proglottids smaller in size; gravid segments larger in size; testes larger in size; ovary larger in size; vitelline gland smaller in size; cirrus sac smaller in size. On the basis of body shape and size of specimen, shape of ovary and testes, hooks arrangement numbering and egg size, a new species *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n. sp. is proposed to accommodate the present worm. However; this species is being reported for the first time from Sindh, Pakistan and *Turdoidea striata* is new host record for the genus; *Oligorchis* Fuhrmann, 1906. On the morphological features and basic characteristic present species is identified as n. sp which were reported first time form Jungle babbler at Sindh and this is the new host record for the genus ; *Oligorchis* Fuhrmann, 1906 in Pakistan (Table- 1).

Table- 1. Comparative morphological features and measurements of *Oligorchis, n.sp* species under laboratory conditions

Species	Present species	<i>O. Lahorensis</i> Khan and Habibullah, 1971	<i>O. raviensis</i> Khan and Habibullah, 1971
Body	1.30-1.34 X 45.55- 51.65	150-180	700-1000 X 1.30-1.70
Hooks	16 in number 0.60-0.86 X 0.12 – 0.12	10 in number 0.013-0.015	12 in number 0.018-0.20
Neck	0.15 X 0.23	Absent	Absent
Scolex	0.14-0.20 X 0.16-0.26	0.12-0.16 X 0.22-0.28	0.23-0.24 X 0.32-0.35
Rostellum	0.02-0.06 X 0.06-0.07	0.04-0.05	0.05
Suckers	0.06-0.09 X 0.9- 0.10	0.09-0.11	0.08-0.09
Cirrus sac	0.4 - 0.47 X 0.12 – 0.14	0.16-0.23 X 0.05	0.18-0.19 X 0.06
Ovary	0.13-0.14 X 0.13-0.17	0.07-0.15 X 0.15-0.37	0.16-0.18 X 0.3-0.35
Tests	0.09 – 0.09 X 0.10 – 0.13	0.07-0.22	0.05-0.20
Mature segments	0.25-1 X 0.25-0.92	0.19-0.22 X 0.16-1.42	0.28-0.34 X 0.68-1.03
Gravid segments	0.45-0.55 X 0.06-0.07	0.28-0.33 X 1.87-2.02	0.37-0.58 X 1.06-1.50
Eggs	0.03 - 0.05 X 0.03 -0.05	Numerous	Numerous
Host	Jungle babbler	<i>Corves splendens splendens</i>	<i>Acredotheres ginginiamus</i>
Locality	N. Feroze, Sindh	Lahore, Pakistan	Lahore, Pakistan

The exploration study was done from the time of October to May during, 2015-16, in which the winged creatures jungle babbler (n=24) were dissected and the information was taken at fortnightly basis. In this manner, two flying creatures were dissected in every month to check the helminths parasites. The consequences of the examination consider demonstrates that the most extreme populace was observed in the months of January and May during, 2016 though, the base populace was seen in the month of June as well (Fig. 3). The analysis of variance showed the significant difference among all the months throughout the year (P<0.05).

DISCUSSION

T. striata is an individual from the Leiothrichidae family found in the Indian subcontinent. This examination study was led during,

2015-16 on *Turdoides striata* (n=24) were caught from taluka Kandiaro, locale Naushahro Feroze, Sindh - Pakistan. [43] reported that the food generally comprised of small insects and their larvae which were seen to be picked up from the adjoining plantations. Jungle babbler (*Turdoides striatus*, Order: Passeriformes, Family: Timalidae) is an insectivore and wide spread passerine of the Indian subcontinent. It's a co-operative breeder and always seen in huge flocks especially during the non-breeding season. Even though they are insectivores only few studies have been carried out to assess their impact on the insect pest species in the agricultural fields as a part of biological control an alternate for insecticides. Jungle babbler is considered as beneficial to crops [44]. As other research study was done by [15] who detailed that the nourishment and bolstering environment of jungle babbler, *Turdoides striatus* *sindianus* observed from June to December at area of Jammu. In addition, this flying creature was found to impart a kind of shared relationship to their sustaining partners. These babblers have omnivorous encouraging propensity with creepy crawlies framing the transcendent segment of their eating regimen. Their plant eats less included organic products, berries, nectar, figs, seeds and grains. Lifting of dead leaves on ground was observed to be the most widely recognized system connected by these babblers for scavenging.

Like this our exploration study is in assenting of them that the predominance of helminth parasites were watched and found the effect of cestode Helminth *Oligorchis kandiarisansis* n.sp in jungle babbler fledgling in various areas of locale Naushahro Feroze which was taken from various eating sources. The insectivore's bird which survive their life in scavenge frame were advantageous for the plants since they bolster creepy crawlies on the plants [45]. At the point when contaminated fowls relocate then they

straightforwardly exchange the infections to different creatures, either by salivation, fecal material or searched upon them. Wild feathered creature species may take a valuable agent display for looking at the route by which illnesses could be spreads from winged animal to fowl and from fledgling to different creatures. All the while, the event of general helminth parasites, for example, nematodes, (33) % were observed during research study. Furthermore, the same kind of research study was conducted which would be supported to this research study in which they found the prevalence of trematode, *L. longicauda* in *T. striata* [46]. The prevalence of helminth parasites was observed during this research study and results are in agreement with the [47] who found the impact of *Hymenolepis* spp. in Jungle babbler bird in same locations of district Naushahro Feroze. Further, the same kind of research study was also conducted which was supported to this research study [48] who observed the *L. longicauda* in *T. striata* (Leiothrichidae) bird at the same vicinity [49]. Besides, the available literature regarding the helminth parasites shows that the birds, *Turdoides striata* have not been properly investigated in Pakistan. Thus, the association among climate transform and the attainment of parasites by the host is imperative, but triumphant infection eventually depends on the communication between these organisms [50].

CONCLUSION

The consequences of this research study completely shows that the jungle babblers are omnivorous in nature and propensity misusing both plant and creature assets accessible to them. Be that as it may, contrasted with plant nourishments, the creature sustenance chiefly are devoured in bigger extents. In this way, we can state that jungle babblers are helpful to human beings. The jungle babblers in this manner help to keep a proficient beware of different hurtful creepy crawlies like many insect pests, predators even though other vertebrate pests, which are damaging to the horticultural, agricultural yields and put away grains from which they sometime infected with helminths parasites.

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